

Materials for the paper “Automated Classification of ADS Disengagements Using Convolutional Neural Networks”

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Appendix A – Performance of Individual Binary Classification Models

These results were derived from the models’ predictions on the 30 test samples, ensuring a consistent evaluation framework across all models. Each model’s predictions were compared against the true labels to compute true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). These outcomes are summarized in Table 1, which provides a detailed breakdown of classification results per sample.

Color Coding:

- **Green:** Correct predictions (True Positives & True Negatives)
- **Red:** Incorrect predictions (False Positives & False Negatives)

It turned out that no FP and FN cases occurred. Therefore, all cells in Table 1 are green.

For each sample, probability scores were recorded for all class labels. If multiple models assigned different labels to a sample, it was marked as "Uncertain." If no model assigned a probability above 0.5, the label was recorded as "Undetermined." Table 2 presents these probability scores and the final assigned labels.

Table 1. Prediction outcomes for all 30 test samples, showing TP, TN, FP, FN for each prediction along with the true label (TL) and the final assigned label (FL).

ID	TL	CL0	CL1	CL2	CL3	CL4	CL6	CL7	CL8	FL
1	0	TP	TN	0						
2	0	TP	TN	0						
3	0	TP	TN	0						
4	0	TP	TN	0						
5	0	TP	TN	0						
6	1	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	1
7	1	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	1
8	1	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	1
9	1	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	1
10	1	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	1
11	2	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	2
12	2	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	2
13	2	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	2
14	2	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	2
15	2	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	2
16	3	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	3
17	3	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	3
18	3	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	3
19	3	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	3
20	3	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	TN	3
21	4	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	4
22	4	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	4
23	4	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	4
24	4	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	4
25	4	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	TN	4
26	6	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	6
27	6	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	6
28	6	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	6
29	6	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	6
30	6	TN	TN	TN	TN	TN	TP	TN	TN	6

Table 2. Results for all 30 test samples, showing the true label (TL), predicted label (FL), and probability score for each sample.

ID	TL	CL0	CL1	CL2	CL3	CL4	CL6	CL7	CL8	FL
1	0	0.6879	0.0035	0.0000	0.0000	0.0021	0.0007	0.0000	0.0000	0
2	0	0.7158	0.0043	0.0000	0.0000	0.0020	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0
3	0	0.7414	0.0053	0.0000	0.0000	0.0019	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0
4	0	0.7454	0.0055	0.0000	0.0000	0.0018	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0
5	0	0.7872	0.0079	0.0000	0.0000	0.0016	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0
6	1	0.0000	0.8231	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1
7	1	0.0000	0.8686	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1
8	1	0.0000	0.8433	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1
9	1	0.0000	0.8596	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1
10	1	0.0000	0.8028	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1
11	2	0.0000	0.0000	0.9982	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	2
12	2	0.0000	0.0000	0.9980	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	2
13	2	0.0000	0.0000	0.9983	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	2
14	2	0.0000	0.0000	0.9982	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	2
15	2	0.0000	0.0000	0.9982	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	2
16	3	0.0000	0.0008	0.0000	0.9982	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3
17	3	0.0000	0.0008	0.0000	0.9982	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3
18	3	0.0000	0.0006	0.0000	0.9987	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3
19	3	0.0000	0.0012	0.0000	0.9974	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3
20	3	0.0000	0.0011	0.0000	0.9975	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3
21	4	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	4
22	4	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	4
23	4	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	4
24	4	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	4
25	4	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	4
26	6	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	0.2878	0.0000	0.9613	0.0000	0.0000	6
27	6	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.3020	0.0000	0.9745	0.0000	0.0000	6
28	6	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	0.2896	0.0000	0.9639	0.0000	0.0000	6
29	6	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.2846	0.0000	0.9431	0.0000	0.0000	6
30	6	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.2852	0.0000	0.9542	0.0000	0.0000	6

Appendix B – SHAP Value Analysis for Model Explanation

The heatmap in Figure 1 provides an overview of feature importance across the different classification models, summarizing how various features influenced predictions. The key components of the visualization include:

- **Color schema:**
 - **Red Shades** indicate positive SHAP values, meaning that the feature increased the likelihood of a particular class being predicted.
 - **Blue Shades** indicate negative SHAP values, meaning that the feature decreased the likelihood of a particular class being predicted.
 - **White** represents that the features were not in the top 5 list of features that most positively or negatively impacted the predictions.
- **Columns:** Each column represents a feature (normalized).
- **Rows:** Each row represents a specific model.
- **Annotations:** The numeric values represent the scaled SHAP values.

The heatmap provided valuable insights into each model's decision-making process and allowed for direct comparisons between models:

- The larger the SHAP value and the darker the red shade, the more strongly a feature contributed positively to the model's prediction. In other words, these features increased the likelihood of the model assigning a given class.
- Conversely, the smaller the SHAP value and the darker the blue shade, the more strongly a feature contributed negatively to the prediction, meaning the feature actively discouraged the model from assigning that class.
- Ideally, each model should focus on a distinct set of features. If the heatmap shows disjoint sets of red and blue shades for each model, it indicates that the models are utilizing different feature subsets for classification.

Figure 1. Visualization of the features that most positively and most negatively impacted the predictions per model.

Appendix C. In-Depth Per-Model SHAP Value Analysis

This section presents a detailed analysis of the SHAP values for each model, highlighting the features that most positively impacted model predictions - features that the models identified as having the most significant influence on the classification of disengagement events. By focusing on these impactful features provides insight into the factors that most effectively shaped the model's decision-making process.

Class 0 - "OBS" (Obstacle) - Disengagement caused by obstacles.

For disengagements caused by obstacles obstructing the vehicle's path, the most influential features were related to object detection, including position and dimensions. The features that had the greatest impact on the model's performance were:

- **objects_position_x_i, objects_position_y_i, objects_position_z_i,**
- **objects_dimensions_z_i.**

These features highlight the model's ability to recognize the importance of nearby objects and their data, enabling it to accurately classify disengagements caused by obstacles obstructing the vehicle's path.

Class 1 - "Safety" (Safety Concerns) - Disengagement caused by safety considerations.

In scenarios where disengagements were triggered by safety concerns, such as objects getting dangerously close or abrupt changes in speed, the most significant features included the detected objects' velocity and orientation, along with the vehicle's linear acceleration and the planned waypoints it was following. The features that had the greatest impact on the model's performance were:

- **closest_object_velocity,**
- **ctrl_cmd.linear_acceleration,**
- **local_dtlane_rw_i,**
- **local_orientation_w_i.**

These features suggest that the model effectively captured situations where disengagements were related to potential safety risks.

Class 2 - “Turnback” (Turnback Maneuvers) - Disengagement caused by turnbacks.

For disengagements resulting from turnbacks, the model’s primary features revolved around the steering angle, the vehicle’s rotational movement (indicated by the twist of the planned path), and linear acceleration. The features with the greatest impact were:

- **ctrl_cmd.steering_angle,**
- **ctrl_cmd.linear_acceleration,**
- **local_orientation_w_i,**
- **local_twist_linear_x_i.**

This demonstrates that the model recognized turnbacks as involving significant changes in steering and rotational movement.

Class 3 - “Pedestrian Crossing” - Disengagement caused by pedestrians crossing the road.

In cases of disengagements due to pedestrians crossing, the most influential features included whether the vehicle was blocked (“is_blocked”) and details about detected objects such as their orientation, labels, dimensions, and positions. The features with the greatest impact were:

- **is_blocked,**
- **objects_label_i,**
- **objects_orientation_w_i, objects_orientation_y_i,**
- **objects_position_x_i.**

These findings show that the model effectively identified the importance of detecting and labeling pedestrians as critical for disengagements caused by pedestrian crossings.

Class 4 - “Localization” (Localization Issues) - Disengagements caused by problems with localization.

For disengagements caused by localization issues (such as insufficient satellite data or the vehicle straying from its planned path), the most important features were related to GPS data, vehicle acceleration, and brake pedal input. The prominent features were:

- **gps_glonass_sig_mask,**
- **ctrl_cmd.linear_acceleration,**

- **brakepedal,**
- **local_orientation_w_i.**

These features reveal that the model recognized localization issues as being tied to GPS signals, vehicle movement (e.g. orientation), and pedal inputs.

Class 6 - “Give Way” (Yielding at Intersections) - Disengagement caused by “give way” situations at intersections.

For disengagements related to “give way” situations, where the vehicle must yield to other traffic at intersections, the model highlighted acceleration and the velocity, orientations, and positions of detected objects as the most influential features. The prominent features were:

- **brakepedal,**
- **closest_object_velocity,**
- **objects_orientation_y_i,**
- **objects_position_x_i.**

These insights indicate that the model understood give-way scenarios typically involve changes in vehicle speed and detection of approaching vehicles or objects.

In conclusion, the SHAP value analysis provided important insights into the features each model prioritized, helping to explain their performance. By identifying the most positively impacting sets of features for each class, the analysis shows that the models focused on different but relevant aspects of the data. This alignment with human intuition supports the models’ accuracy and helps explain why they performed well.

Appendix D. Cross-Model SHAP Value Analysis

This section details the comparative SHAP value analysis performed on the 6 models to examine how different disengagement classes rely on distinct or overlapping features. The analysis quantifies the extent to which positively and negatively contributing features are shared between pairs of classes.

The following tables summarize the feature overlap for both positive and negative contributors. A low overlap suggests that the models rely on distinct decision-making patterns, while a higher overlap indicates that some disengagement classes may share underlying patterns in the data. Refer to Figure 1 in Appendix A for the SHAP value heatmap, which visually represents feature contributions across the models.

Table 1 presents the overlap of positively contributing features between the six disengagement classes. The number of positive features identified for each class is indicated in square brackets next to the class label. The values in the table represent the percentage of shared features between each pair of classes, calculated relative to the smaller feature set of the two.

Table 1. Overlap of positively contributing features.

+	Class 0 [4]	Class 1 [5]	Class 2 [4]	Class 3 [5]	Class 4 [5]	Class 6 [4]
Class 0 [4]		0	0	0.25	0.25	0.25
Class 1 [5]	0		0.25	0.2	0.2	0.25
Class 2 [4]	0	0.25		0	0.25	0
Class 3 [5]	0.25	0.2	0		0.2	0.5
Class 4 [5]	0.25	0.2	0.25	0.2		0.5
Class 6 [4]	0.25	0.25	0	0.5	0.5	

Table presents the overlap of negatively contributing features between the six disengagement classes. Similar to the previous table, the number of negative features identified for each class is listed in square brackets. The values represent the percentage of shared negative features between pairs, calculated relative to the smaller feature set.

Table 2. Overlap of negatively contributing features.

-	Class 0 [3]	Class 1 [3]	Class 2 [4]	Class 3 [3]	Class 4 [4]	Class 6 [4]
Class 0 [3]		0	0	~0.33	~0.33	0
Class 1 [3]	0		~0.33	~0.66	0	0
Class 2 [4]	0	~0.33		0	0	0.25
Class 3 [3]	~0.33	~0.66	0		~0.33	0
Class 4 [4]	~0.33	0	0	~0.33		0
Class 6 [4]	0	0	0.25	0	0	

The results show that while some model pairs have completely disjoint feature sets, others share a limited number of positive or negative features. However, the overlap remains relatively small or nonexistent in most cases. The main observations include:

- **Minimal Overlap:** Most class pairs exhibit low feature sharing, suggesting that the models differentiate disengagement classes using distinct patterns.
- **Instances of Higher Overlap:** A few class pairs (e.g., Class 3 and Class 6 for positive features and Class 1 & Class 3 for negative features) show higher overlap, indicating potential similarities in how these disengagement events are characterized.

The limited feature overlap reinforces that the models effectively distinguish disengagement types while allowing for some shared decision-making elements where disengagement reasons might have similar patterns in the data.

This comparative analysis provides deeper insights into how the models differentiate disengagement events and highlights the degree of feature uniqueness across classes.